

Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 13

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Abstract

*During past years author worked with **borderedmagic squares** of even number blocks. These are based on equal sums magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8, 10, etc. This type of work is an extension of classical bordered magic squares. In case of multiples of 4, the extension is made for **pandiagonal** magic squares [23]. For multiples of order 6 refer Taneja [24]. Recently, author worked on multiples of 3, 5, 7 and 9. These are based on different sums of magic squares of order 3, 5, 7, 9 and 11 [29, 30, 31, 32, 33]. This work is for multiples of 13. It is revised and enlarged version of previous work. We have worked with 25 different types of magic squares of order 13. Total work is up to order 130, but due to space problems the examples given here are only up to order 52. Higher order examples can be seen in **Excel files** attached with the work.*

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1 Introduction

During past years author [2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8] worked with **block-wise** magic squares from orders 12 to 47. Author [9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14] also worked with **bordered** magic squares. The study on **bordered** magic squares is extended to **block-bordered** magic squares [15, 16, 17]. This is specially done for the magic squares of orders p and $2p$, where p is a prime number. This study is still extended to **block-wise bordered** magic squares [18, 19, 20, 21]. Some connection with Pythagorean triples and area-representations are also made [23, 24, 25, 26, 27]. The main property of **bordered** magic squares is that if we remove external borders, still we get **sub-bordered** magic squares, i.e., each layer in itself lead us to magic squares. In many cases, the properties of **bordered** magic square are separated by **even** and **odd** orders magic squares. In many cases, we get good properties for the **even** order **bordered** magic squares. In some cases, we have to use fractional numbers to reach minimum perfect square sum of entries. For more study on **bordered** magic squares refer H. White's web-site [1].

The idea of bordered magic squares is already discussed by H. White's web-site [1] where the borders are of **single digits**. Borders multiples of even numbers starting from order 4 are done extensively by author [23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28].

1.1 Summary of Bordered Magic Squares

1.1.1 Odd Numbers Multiples

- **Single Digit:** Bordered magic squares based on single digit [9, 10, 1].
- **Three Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 3 [29].
- **Five Digits:** Bordered magic squares multiples of magic squares of order 5 [30].
- **Seven Digits:** Bordered magic squares multiples of magic squares of order 7 [31].
- **Nine Digits:** Bordered magic squares multiples of magic squares of order 9 [32]
- **Eleven Digits:** Bordered magic squares multiples of magic squares of order 11 [33]
- **Eleven Digits:** Bordered magic squares multiples of magic squares of order 13 [34] (This work)

1.1.2 Even Numbers Multiples

- **Two Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic rectangles multiples of 2 [74, 75, 63, 64, 64, 65].
- **Four Digits:** Bordered magic squares multiples of magic squares of order 4 [23].
- **Six Digits:** Bordered magic squares multiples of magic squares of order 6 [24].
- **Eight Digits:** Bordered magic squares multiples of magic squares of order 8 [25].
- **Ten Digits:** Bordered magic squares multiples of magic squares of order 10 [26].
- **Twelve Digits:** Bordered magic squares multiples of magic squares of order 12 [27].
- **Fourteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares multiples of magic squares of order 14 [28].

The work on even number multiples is with equal sums blocks of magic squares. The work on odd number multiples is with different sum magic squares.

This work is for bordered magic squares multiples of 13. Here are working with 25 different types of magic square of order 13. The procedure, how these bordered magic squares are obtained is also given. Higher orders examples can be seen in **Excel file** attached with this work.

2 Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 13

Let's consider following 25 magic squares of order 13.

pan	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	
1105	1	25	36	47	58	69	80	104	115	126	137	148	159	1105
1105	145	169	11	22	33	44	55	66	90	101	112	123	134	1105
1105	120	131	155	166	8	19	30	41	65	76	87	98	109	1105
1105	95	106	130	141	152	163	5	16	27	51	62	73	84	1105
1105	70	81	92	116	127	138	149	160	2	26	37	48	59	1105
1105	45	56	67	91	102	113	124	135	146	157	12	23	34	1105
1105	20	31	42	53	77	88	99	110	121	132	156	167	9	1105
1105	164	6	17	28	52	63	74	85	96	107	118	142	153	1105
1105	139	150	161	3	14	38	49	60	71	82	93	117	128	1105
1105	114	125	136	147	158	13	24	35	46	57	68	79	103	1105
1105	89	100	111	122	133	144	168	10	21	32	43	54	78	1105
1105	64	75	86	97	108	119	143	154	165	7	18	29	40	1105
1105	39	50	61	72	83	94	105	129	140	151	162	4	15	1105
1	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105

2	mgc	1187	1113	1045	1043	1089	1089	1123	1119	1165	1167	1099	1021	1105
156	147	149	151	153	155	157	9	7	5	3	1	12	1105	
2	36	44	42	40	38	137	138	140	142	144	34	168	1105	
4	145	52	124	122	120	119	56	58	60	54	25	166	1105	
6	143	45	102	98	100	65	64	62	104	125	27	164	1105	
8	141	47	61	94	97	77	79	78	109	123	29	162	1105	
10	139	49	63	74	84	89	82	96	107	121	31	160	1105	
11	35	117	103	75	83	85	87	95	67	53	135	159	1105	
154	37	115	101	90	88	81	86	80	69	55	133	16	1105	
152	39	113	99	92	73	93	91	76	71	57	131	18	1105	
150	41	111	66	72	70	105	106	108	68	59	129	20	1105	
148	43	116	46	48	50	51	114	112	110	118	127	22	1105	
146	136	126	128	130	132	33	32	30	28	26	134	24	1105	
158	23	21	19	17	15	13	161	163	165	167	169	14	1105	
1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105

3	mgc	1257	1101	993	1149	1173	1066	1098	1121	1013	1037	1193	1059	1105
156	147	149	151	153	155	157	9	7	5	3	1	12	1105	
2	36	44	42	40	38	137	138	140	142	144	34	168	1105	
4	145	66	115	74	71	108	76	64	113	78	25	166	1105	
6	143	79	65	111	72	67	116	77	69	109	27	164	1105	
8	141	110	75	70	112	80	63	114	73	68	29	162	1105	
10	139	84	52	119	89	45	121	82	50	123	31	160	1105	
11	35	124	83	48	117	85	53	122	87	46	135	159	1105	
154	37	47	120	88	49	125	81	51	118	86	133	16	1105	
152	39	102	97	56	107	90	58	100	95	60	131	18	1105	
150	41	61	101	93	54	103	98	59	105	91	129	20	1105	
148	43	92	57	106	94	62	99	96	55	104	127	22	1105	
146	136	126	128	130	132	33	32	30	28	26	134	24	1105	
158	23	21	19	17	15	13	161	163	165	167	169	14	1105	
1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105

4	mgc	1076	939	1370	1069	1097	1180	719	1201	1419	1012	1135	1123	1105
21	26	164	132	12	160	3	9	134	143	131	19	151	1105	
149	144	6	38	158	10	167	161	36	27	39	136	34	1105	
44	126	115	119	69	47	54	121	70	108	62	140	30	1105	
153	17	55	51	101	123	116	49	100	104	66	127	43	1105	
166	4	45	125	76	92	87	84	86	53	117	139	31	1105	
146	24	57	113	94	78	83	97	73	46	124	29	141	1105	
13	157	112	58	88	82	85	74	96	99	71	33	137	1105	
2	168	109	61	90	80	81	95	79	65	105	5	165	1105	
25	145	56	114	77	93	89	75	91	120	50	18	152	1105	
16	154	106	64	98	63	67	59	68	122	118	142	28	1105	
169	1	110	60	72	107	103	111	102	48	52	147	23	1105	
159	11	155	14	129	162	163	35	20	40	148	37	32	1105	
42	128	15	156	41	8	7	135	150	130	22	133	138	1105	
1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105

5	mgc	1092	918	1402	1054	1097	1100	719	1201	1437	997	1133	1110	1105	
		21	26	164	132	12	160	3	9	134	143	131	19	151	1105
		149	144	6	38	158	10	167	161	36	27	39	136	34	1105
		44	126	115	119	69	47	54	121	70	108	62	140	30	1105
		153	17	55	51	101	123	116	49	100	104	66	127	43	1105
		166	4	45	125	94	97	77	79	78	53	117	139	31	1105
		146	24	57	113	74	84	89	82	96	46	124	29	141	1105
		13	157	112	58	90	83	85	87	80	99	71	33	137	1105
		2	168	109	61	75	88	81	86	95	65	105	5	165	1105
		25	145	56	114	92	73	93	91	76	120	50	18	152	1105
		16	154	106	64	98	63	67	59	68	122	118	142	28	1105
		169	1	110	60	72	107	103	111	102	48	52	147	23	1105
		159	11	155	14	129	162	163	35	20	40	148	37	32	1105
		42	128	15	156	41	8	7	135	150	130	22	133	138	1105
		1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105

6	mgc	1141	968	1335	1122	965	1107	783	1264	1367	926	1283	999	1105	
		21	26	164	132	12	160	3	9	134	143	131	19	151	1105
		149	144	6	38	158	10	167	161	36	27	39	136	34	1105
		44	126	66	115	74	71	108	76	82	50	123	140	30	1105
		153	17	79	65	111	72	67	116	122	87	46	127	43	1105
		166	4	110	75	70	112	80	63	51	118	86	139	31	1105
		146	24	84	52	119	89	45	121	64	113	78	29	141	1105
		13	157	124	83	48	117	85	53	77	69	109	33	137	1105
		2	168	47	120	88	49	125	81	114	73	68	5	165	1105
		25	145	102	97	56	107	90	58	100	95	60	18	152	1105
		16	154	61	101	93	54	103	98	59	105	91	142	28	1105
		169	1	92	57	106	94	62	99	96	55	104	147	23	1105
		159	11	155	14	129	162	163	35	20	40	148	37	32	1105
		42	128	15	156	41	8	7	135	150	130	22	133	138	1105
		1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105

7	mgc	1167	968	1348	1035	978	1058	828	1265	1434	932	1233	1014	1105	
		21	26	164	132	12	160	3	9	134	143	131	19	151	1105
		149	144	6	38	158	10	167	161	36	27	39	136	34	1105
		44	126	52	124	122	120	119	56	58	60	54	140	30	1105
		153	17	45	102	98	100	65	64	62	104	125	127	43	1105
		166	4	47	61	94	97	77	79	78	109	123	139	31	1105
		146	24	49	63	74	84	89	82	96	107	121	29	141	1105
		13	157	117	103	90	83	85	87	80	67	53	33	137	1105
		2	168	115	101	75	88	81	86	95	69	55	5	165	1105
		25	145	113	99	92	73	93	91	76	71	57	18	152	1105
		16	154	111	66	72	70	105	106	108	68	59	142	28	1105
		169	1	116	46	48	50	51	114	112	110	118	147	23	1105
		159	11	155	14	129	162	163	35	20	40	148	37	32	1105
		42	128	15	156	41	8	7	135	150	130	22	133	138	1105
		1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105

8	mgc	1154	976	1393	1031	926	1185	813	1201	1366	952	1241	1022	1105	
		21	26	164	132	12	160	3	9	134	143	131	19	151	1105
		149	144	6	38	158	10	167	161	36	27	39	136	34	1105
		44	126	82	87	86	78	92	67	103	111	59	140	30	1105
		153	17	89	85	81	79	91	102	68	49	121	127	43	1105
		166	4	84	83	88	96	74	99	71	48	122	139	31	1105
		146	24	80	76	77	97	95	62	108	113	57	29	141	1105
		13	157	90	94	93	75	73	63	107	116	54	33	137	1105
		2	168	105	61	64	100	101	98	66	53	117	5	165	1105
		25	145	65	109	106	70	69	104	72	47	123	18	152	1105
		16	154	45	120	115	51	112	114	46	110	52	142	28	1105
		169	1	125	50	55	119	58	56	124	118	60	147	23	1105
		159	11	155	14	129	162	163	35	20	40	148	37	32	1105
		42	128	15	156	41	8	7	135	150	130	22	133	138	1105
		1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105

9	mgc	1156	975	1388	1036	916	1179	821	1224	1366	946	1233	1020	1105
21	26	164	132	12	160	3	9	134	143	131	19	151	1105	
149	144	6	38	158	10	167	161	36	27	39	136	34	1105	
44	126	73	79	85	91	97	67	103	116	54	140	30	1105	
153	17	90	96	77	78	84	102	68	48	122	127	43	1105	
166	4	82	83	89	95	76	99	71	49	121	139	31	1105	
146	24	94	75	81	87	88	62	108	113	57	29	141	1105	
13	157	86	92	93	74	80	63	107	111	59	33	137	1105	
2	168	105	61	64	100	101	98	66	53	117	5	165	1105	
25	145	65	109	106	70	69	104	72	47	123	18	152	1105	
16	154	46	120	115	51	112	114	45	110	52	142	28	1105	
169	1	124	50	55	119	58	56	125	118	60	147	23	1105	
159	11	155	14	129	162	163	35	20	40	148	37	32	1105	
42	128	15	156	41	8	7	135	150	130	22	133	138	1105	
1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	

10	mgc	1154	974	1395	1031	937	1181	809	1205	1366	931	1236	1041	1105
21	26	164	132	12	160	3	9	134	143	131	19	151	1105	
149	144	6	38	158	10	167	161	36	27	39	136	34	1105	
44	126	94	97	77	79	78	67	103	113	57	140	30	1105	
153	17	74	84	89	82	96	102	68	49	121	127	43	1105	
166	4	90	83	85	87	80	99	71	48	122	139	31	1105	
146	24	75	88	81	86	95	62	108	111	59	29	141	1105	
13	157	92	73	93	91	76	63	107	116	54	33	137	1105	
2	168	105	61	64	100	101	98	66	53	117	5	165	1105	
25	145	65	109	106	70	69	104	72	47	123	18	152	1105	
16	154	46	120	115	51	112	114	45	110	52	142	28	1105	
169	1	124	50	55	119	58	56	125	118	60	147	23	1105	
159	11	155	14	129	162	163	35	20	40	148	37	32	1105	
42	128	15	156	41	8	7	135	150	130	22	133	138	1105	
1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	

11	mgc	1152	976	1370	1031	904	1179	826	1195	1387	947	1241	1052	1105
21	26	164	132	12	160	3	9	134	143	131	19	151	1105	
149	144	6	38	158	10	167	161	36	27	39	136	34	1105	
44	126	61	69	77	85	93	101	109	116	54	140	30	1105	
153	17	100	108	67	68	76	84	92	49	121	127	43	1105	
166	4	83	91	99	107	66	74	75	48	122	139	31	1105	
146	24	73	81	82	90	98	106	65	113	57	29	141	1105	
13	157	105	64	72	80	88	89	97	111	59	33	137	1105	
2	168	95	96	104	63	71	79	87	53	117	5	165	1105	
25	145	78	86	94	102	103	62	70	47	123	18	152	1105	
16	154	46	112	120	51	115	114	45	110	52	142	28	1105	
169	1	124	58	50	119	55	56	125	118	60	147	23	1105	
159	11	155	14	129	162	163	35	20	40	148	37	32	1105	
42	128	15	156	41	8	7	135	150	130	22	133	138	1105	
1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	

12	mgc	1155	976	1405	1024	952	1167	818	1253	1319	909	1241	1041	1105
21	26	164	132	12	160	3	9	134	143	131	19	151	1105	
149	144	6	38	158	10	167	161	36	27	39	136	34	1105	
44	126	102	98	65	100	64	62	104	116	54	140	30	1105	
153	17	61	94	97	77	79	78	109	47	123	127	43	1105	
166	4	101	74	84	89	82	96	69	53	117	139	31	1105	
146	24	103	90	83	85	87	80	67	113	57	29	141	1105	
13	157	63	75	88	81	86	95	107	111	59	33	137	1105	
2	168	99	92	73	93	91	76	71	48	122	5	165	1105	
25	145	66	72	105	70	106	108	68	49	121	18	152	1105	
16	154	51	112	120	46	115	114	45	110	52	142	28	1105	
169	1	119	58	50	124	55	56	125	118	60	147	23	1105	
159	11	155	14	129	162	163	35	20	40	148	37	32	1105	
42	128	15	156	41	8	7	135	150	130	22	133	138	1105	
1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	

13	mgc	1016	1239	967	1452	906	1268	960	1079	1105	903	1105	1260	1105
82	87	86	91	79	98	72	51	119	43	127	159	11	1105	
89	85	81	92	78	105	65	60	110	134	36	1	169	1105	
84	83	88	74	96	102	68	56	114	37	133	8	162	1105	
80	76	77	95	97	99	71	58	112	144	26	6	164	1105	
90	94	93	73	75	63	107	121	49	39	131	5	165	1105	
100	64	101	104	62	61	103	118	52	35	135	147	23	1105	
70	106	69	66	108	67	109	57	113	139	31	152	18	1105	
122	123	59	53	54	55	125	124	50	140	30	157	13	1105	
48	47	111	117	116	115	45	120	46	44	126	155	15	1105	
136	28	130	27	25	129	33	132	29	138	128	4	166	1105	
34	142	40	143	145	41	137	38	141	42	32	149	21	1105	
14	146	151	154	9	158	153	150	7	148	3	2	10	1105	
156	24	19	16	161	12	17	20	163	22	167	160	168	1105	
1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	

14	mgc	1007	1232	975	1462	906	1297	932	1071	1110	903	1105	1260	1105
73	79	85	91	97	98	72	51	119	43	127	159	11	1105	
90	96	77	78	84	105	65	60	110	134	36	1	169	1105	
82	83	89	95	76	102	68	56	114	37	133	8	162	1105	
94	75	81	87	88	99	71	58	112	144	26	6	164	1105	
86	92	93	74	80	63	107	121	49	39	131	5	165	1105	
100	64	101	104	62	61	103	118	52	35	135	147	23	1105	
70	106	69	66	108	67	109	57	113	139	31	152	18	1105	
122	123	59	53	54	55	125	124	50	140	30	157	13	1105	
48	47	111	117	116	115	45	120	46	44	126	155	15	1105	
136	28	130	27	25	129	33	132	29	138	128	4	166	1105	
34	142	40	143	145	41	137	38	141	42	32	149	21	1105	
14	146	151	154	9	158	153	150	7	148	3	2	10	1105	
156	24	19	16	161	12	17	20	163	22	167	160	168	1105	
1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	

15	mgc	1028	1234	963	1443	906	1282	935	1095	1106	903	1105	1260	1105
94	97	77	79	78	98	72	51	119	43	127	159	11	1105	
74	84	89	82	96	105	65	60	110	134	36	1	169	1105	
90	83	85	87	80	102	68	56	114	37	133	8	162	1105	
75	88	81	86	95	99	71	58	112	144	26	6	164	1105	
92	73	93	91	76	63	107	121	49	39	131	5	165	1105	
100	64	101	104	62	61	103	118	52	35	135	147	23	1105	
70	106	69	66	108	67	109	57	113	139	31	152	18	1105	
122	123	59	53	54	55	125	124	50	140	30	157	13	1105	
48	47	111	117	116	115	45	120	46	44	126	155	15	1105	
136	28	130	27	25	129	33	132	29	138	128	4	166	1105	
34	142	40	143	145	41	137	38	141	42	32	149	21	1105	
14	146	151	154	9	158	153	150	7	148	3	2	10	1105	
156	24	19	16	161	12	17	20	163	22	167	160	168	1105	
1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	

16	mgc	1006	1232	980	1433	927	1272	960	1069	1177	895	1132	1177	1105
61	69	77	85	93	101	109	51	119	43	127	159	11	1105	
100	108	67	68	76	84	92	121	49	144	26	1	169	1105	
83	91	99	107	66	74	75	56	114	37	133	8	162	1105	
73	81	82	90	98	106	65	58	112	134	36	6	164	1105	
105	64	72	80	88	89	97	60	110	39	131	5	165	1105	
95	96	104	63	71	79	87	118	52	35	135	147	23	1105	
78	86	94	102	103	62	70	57	113	139	31	152	18	1105	
122	123	53	55	59	54	125	124	50	140	30	157	13	1105	
48	47	117	115	111	116	45	120	46	44	126	155	15	1105	
130	28	136	27	25	129	33	132	29	138	128	4	166	1105	
40	142	34	143	145	41	137	38	141	42	32	149	21	1105	
14	146	151	154	9	158	153	150	7	148	3	2	10	1105	
156	24	19	16	161	12	17	20	163	22	167	160	168	1105	
1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	

17	mgc	1047	1222	1007	1456	859	1236	958	1053	1149	926	1142	1205	1105
102	98	100	65	64	62	104	51	119	43	127	157	13	1105	
61	94	97	77	79	78	109	121	49	144	26	1	169	1105	
101	74	84	89	82	96	69	56	114	37	133	8	162	1105	
103	90	83	85	87	80	67	58	112	134	36	6	164	1105	
63	75	88	81	86	95	107	60	110	39	131	5	165	1105	
99	92	73	93	91	76	71	118	52	35	135	147	23	1105	
66	72	70	105	106	108	68	57	113	139	31	152	18	1105	
122	123	53	55	59	54	125	124	50	140	30	159	11	1105	
48	47	117	115	111	116	45	120	46	44	126	155	15	1105	
130	28	136	27	25	129	33	132	29	138	128	4	166	1105	
40	142	34	143	145	41	137	38	141	42	32	149	21	1105	
14	146	151	154	9	158	153	150	7	148	3	2	10	1105	
156	24	19	16	161	12	17	20	163	22	167	160	168	1105	
1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105

18	mgc	990	1187	1084	1415	974	1257	952	1020	1105	1058	1100	1118	1105
52	124	122	120	119	56	58	60	54	43	127	159	11	1105	
45	102	98	100	65	64	62	104	125	134	36	1	169	1105	
47	61	94	97	77	79	78	109	123	37	133	8	162	1105	
49	63	74	84	89	82	96	107	121	139	31	6	164	1105	
117	103	90	83	85	87	80	67	53	39	131	5	165	1105	
115	101	75	88	81	86	95	69	55	35	135	147	23	1105	
113	99	92	73	93	91	76	71	57	144	26	152	18	1105	
111	66	72	70	105	106	108	68	59	140	30	157	13	1105	
116	46	48	50	51	114	112	110	118	44	126	155	15	1105	
136	28	33	27	25	129	33	132	29	138	128	4	166	1105	
34	142	137	143	145	41	40	38	141	42	32	149	21	1105	
14	146	151	154	9	158	153	150	7	148	3	2	10	1105	
156	24	19	16	161	12	17	20	163	22	167	160	168	1105	
1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105

19	mgc	967	1231	942	1516	907	1251	1002	1005	1105	1032	1100	1202	1105
66	115	74	71	108	76	82	50	123	43	127	159	11	1105	
79	65	111	72	67	116	122	87	46	134	36	6	164	1105	
110	75	70	112	80	63	51	118	86	37	133	8	162	1105	
84	52	119	89	45	121	64	113	78	144	26	1	169	1105	
124	83	48	117	85	53	77	69	109	39	131	5	165	1105	
47	120	88	49	125	81	114	73	68	35	135	147	23	1105	
102	97	56	107	90	58	100	95	60	139	31	152	18	1105	
61	101	93	54	103	98	59	105	91	140	30	157	13	1105	
92	57	106	94	62	99	96	55	104	44	126	155	15	1105	
136	28	130	27	25	129	33	132	29	138	128	4	166	1105	
34	142	40	143	145	41	137	38	141	42	32	149	21	1105	
14	146	151	154	9	158	153	150	7	148	3	2	10	1105	
156	24	19	16	161	12	17	20	163	22	167	160	168	1105	
1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105

20	mgc	1047	1043	1089	1105	1254	1122	1016	1153	1095	1050	1105	1181	1105
36	44	42	40	38	137	138	140	142	144	34	159	11	1105	
145	52	124	122	120	119	56	58	60	54	25	152	18	1105	
143	45	102	98	100	65	64	62	104	125	27	8	162	1105	
141	47	61	94	97	77	79	78	109	123	29	1	169	1105	
139	49	63	74	84	89	82	96	107	121	31	5	165	1105	
35	117	103	75	83	85	87	95	67	53	135	6	164	1105	
37	115	101	90	88	81	86	80	69	55	133	147	23	1105	
39	113	99	92	73	93	91	76	71	57	131	157	13	1105	
41	111	66	72	70	105	106	108	68	59	129	155	15	1105	
43	116	46	48	50	51	114	112	110	118	127	4	166	1105	
136	126	128	130	132	33	32	30	28	26	134	149	21	1105	
14	9	151	154	146	158	153	150	7	148	3	2	10	1105	
156	161	19	16	24	12	17	20	163	22	167	160	168	1105	
1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105

21	mgc	931	1184	830	1419	1156	1189	879	1204	1021	1035	1105	1307	1105
136	116	33	45	38	53	58	145	141	129	41	155	15	1105	
34	54	137	125	132	117	112	25	29	44	126	8	162	1105	
124	46	109	103	66	79	68	74	96	118	52	1	169	1105	
32	138	61	67	104	91	102	64	106	144	26	6	164	1105	
131	39	73	97	86	87	82	100	70	48	122	5	165	1105	
120	50	62	108	81	85	89	94	76	135	35	147	23	1105	
59	111	90	80	88	83	84	93	77	49	121	152	18	1105	
128	42	95	75	107	99	69	72	78	43	127	157	13	1105	
30	140	105	65	63	71	101	98	92	55	115	159	11	1105	
28	142	119	123	27	36	31	133	56	110	130	4	166	1105	
113	57	51	47	143	134	139	37	114	60	40	149	21	1105	
14	146	151	154	9	158	153	150	7	148	3	2	10	1105	
156	24	19	16	161	12	17	20	163	22	167	160	168	1105	
1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	

22	mgc	999	1187	820	1385	1163	1184	930	1201	994	1003	1105	1289	1105
136	116	33	45	38	53	58	145	141	129	41	155	15	1105	
34	54	137	125	132	117	112	25	29	44	126	5	165	1105	
124	46	102	98	100	65	64	62	104	118	52	8	162	1105	
32	138	61	94	97	77	79	78	109	135	35	6	164	1105	
131	39	63	74	84	89	82	96	107	48	122	1	169	1105	
120	50	103	90	83	85	87	80	67	144	26	147	23	1105	
59	111	101	75	88	81	86	95	69	49	121	152	18	1105	
128	42	99	92	73	93	91	76	71	43	127	157	13	1105	
30	140	66	72	70	105	106	108	68	55	115	159	11	1105	
28	142	133	123	27	36	31	119	56	110	130	4	166	1105	
113	57	37	47	143	134	139	51	114	60	40	149	21	1105	
14	146	151	154	9	158	153	150	7	148	3	2	10	1105	
156	24	19	16	161	12	17	20	163	22	167	160	168	1105	
1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	

23	mgc	900	1214	811	1416	1147	1193	928	1218	1003	971	1144	1315	1105
136	116	33	45	38	53	58	145	141	129	41	155	15	1105	
34	54	137	125	132	117	112	25	29	44	126	8	162	1105	
124	46	86	81	88	90	80	68	102	118	52	5	165	1105	
32	138	87	85	83	93	77	72	98	135	35	6	164	1105	
131	39	82	89	84	74	96	108	62	48	122	1	169	1105	
120	50	94	92	91	73	75	105	65	144	26	147	23	1105	
59	111	76	78	79	95	97	70	100	49	121	152	18	1105	
128	42	67	109	107	106	66	71	69	43	127	157	13	1105	
30	140	103	61	63	64	104	101	99	55	115	159	11	1105	
28	142	133	123	27	36	31	119	56	110	130	4	166	1105	
113	57	37	47	143	134	139	51	114	60	40	149	21	1105	
14	146	151	154	9	158	153	150	7	148	3	2	10	1105	
156	24	19	16	161	12	17	20	163	22	167	160	168	1105	
1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	

24	mgc	891	1205	820	1424	1126	1194	936	1207	1003	1003	1152	1299	1105
136	116	33	45	38	53	58	145	141	129	41	147	23	1105	
34	54	137	125	132	117	112	25	29	44	126	8	162	1105	
124	46	73	79	85	91	97	68	102	118	52	5	165	1105	
32	138	90	96	77	78	84	72	98	144	26	6	164	1105	
131	39	82	83	89	95	76	108	62	48	122	1	169	1105	
120	50	94	75	81	87	88	105	65	135	35	155	15	1105	
59	111	86	92	93	74	80	70	100	49	121	152	18	1105	
128	42	67	109	107	106	66	71	69	43	127	157	13	1105	
30	140	103	61	63	64	104	101	99	55	115	159	11	1105	
28	142	133	123	27	36	31	119	56	110	130	4	166	1105	
113	57	37	47	143	134	139	51	114	60	40	149	21	1105	
14	146	151	154	9	158	153	150	7	148	3	2	10	1105	
156	24	19	16	161	12	17	20	163	22	167	160	168	1105	
1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	

25	mgc	890	1207	818	1424	1147	1196	926	1186	1003	988	1153	1322	1105
136	116	33	45	38	53	58	145	141	129	41	147	23	1105	
34	54	137	125	132	117	112	25	29	44	126	6	164	1105	
124	46	94	97	79	77	78	68	102	118	52	5	165	1105	
32	138	74	84	89	82	96	72	98	144	26	8	162	1105	
131	39	90	83	85	87	80	105	65	48	122	1	169	1105	
120	50	75	88	81	86	95	108	62	135	35	155	15	1105	
59	111	92	73	91	93	76	70	100	49	121	152	18	1105	
128	42	67	109	107	106	66	71	69	43	127	157	13	1105	
30	140	103	61	63	64	104	101	99	55	115	159	11	1105	
28	142	133	123	27	36	31	119	56	110	130	4	166	1105	
113	57	37	47	143	134	139	51	114	60	40	149	21	1105	
14	146	151	154	9	158	153	150	7	148	3	2	10	1105	
156	24	19	16	161	12	17	20	163	22	167	160	168	1105	
1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	

2.1 Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 130 and 117

Let's consider **bordered** magic square of orders 9 and 10 given by

9x9									369	
	8	80	78	76	75	12	14	16	10	369
	1	58	54	56	21	20	18	60	81	369
	3	17	50	53	33	35	34	65	79	369
	5	19	30	40	45	38	52	63	77	369
	73	59	31	39	41	43	51	23	9	369
	71	57	46	44	37	42	36	25	11	369
	69	55	48	29	49	47	32	27	13	369
	67	22	28	26	61	62	64	24	15	369
	72	2	4	6	7	70	68	66	74	369
	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

10x10											505
	91	86	16	84	18	14	4	98	2	92	505
	13	26	20	80	82	69	31	71	25	88	505
	89	23	64	62	35	68	36	38	78	12	505
	11	24	34	49	54	43	56	67	77	90	505
	96	29	40	44	55	50	53	61	72	5	505
	1	79	42	58	45	52	47	59	22	100	505
	93	74	60	51	48	57	46	41	27	8	505
	7	73	63	39	66	33	65	37	28	94	505
	95	76	81	21	19	32	70	30	75	6	505
	9	15	85	17	83	87	97	3	99	10	505
	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

The entries of above two magic squares are sequential numbers starting from 1:

$$D_{9 \times 9} := \{1, 2, \dots, 80, 81\}$$

$$D_{10 \times 10} := \{1, 2, \dots, 99, 100\}$$

The property of **bordered** magic squares is that removing the upper borders still we are left with magic squares of sequential values.

Multiplying each entry of above two magic squares of orders 9 and 10 by 169, we get

9x9										62361
	1352	13520	13182	12844	12675	2028	2366	2704	1690	62361
	169	9802	9126	9464	3549	3380	3042	10140	13689	62361
	507	2873	8450	8957	5577	5915	5746	10985	13351	62361
	845	3211	5070	6760	7605	6422	8788	10647	13013	62361
	12337	9971	5239	6591	6929	7267	8619	3887	1521	62361
	11999	9633	7774	7436	6253	7098	6084	4225	1859	62361
	11661	9295	8112	4901	8281	7943	5408	4563	2197	62361
	11323	3718	4732	4394	10309	10478	10816	4056	2535	62361
	12168	338	676	1014	1183	11830	11492	11154	12506	62361
	62361	62361	62361	62361	62361	62361	62361	62361	62361	62361

10x10											85345
	15379	14534	2704	14196	3042	2366	676	16562	338	15548	85345
	2197	4394	3380	13520	13858	11661	5239	11999	4225	14872	85345
	15041	3887	10816	10478	5915	11492	6084	6422	13182	2028	85345
	1859	4056	5746	8281	9126	7267	9464	11323	13013	15210	85345
	16224	4901	6760	7436	9295	8450	8957	10309	12168	845	85345
	169	13351	7098	9802	7605	8788	7943	9971	3718	16900	85345
	15717	12506	10140	8619	8112	9633	7774	6929	4563	1352	85345
	1183	12337	10647	6591	11154	5577	10985	6253	4732	15886	85345
	16055	12844	13689	3549	3211	5408	11830	5070	12675	1014	85345
	1521	2535	14365	2873	14027	14703	16393	507	16731	1690	85345
	85345	85345	85345	85345	85345	85345	85345	85345	85345	85345	85345

In this case, the entries distributions of these two magic squares are given by 169, 338, 13520, 13689

$$D_{9 \times 9} := \{169, 338, \dots, 13520, 13689\}$$

$$D_{10 \times 10} := \{169, 338, \dots, 16731, 16900\}$$

Let's replace each entry in above two magic squares of orders 13 and 14 by above two magic squares of order 11. The entries chosen in these magic squares are as given below:

169 → 1, 2, ..., 169
338 → 170, 171, ..., 338
363 → 339, 340, ..., 507
... →
... →

This lead us to two big **block-bordered** magic squares of orders 117 and 130. Since these two magic squares are very big, these are given in two **excel files** attached with this work. There are total 25 magic squares of orders 117 and 130 multiples of order 13.

The multiples blocks are 25 different kinds of magic squares of order 13. Based on these two big magic squares we get the following magic squares.

2.2 Magic Squares of Order 52

Below are three examples of magic squares of order 52 obtained from magic squares of order 154. It is obtained by the application of the formula $\frac{a^2 - b^2}{2}$, $a > b$, i.e., subtract $\frac{130^2 - 52^2}{2} := 7098$ from each entry of magic square order 130, we get the following three magic squares of order 52:

10	mgc	70134	70854	69170	70626	71002	70026	71514	69930	69286	71026	69806	70586	70330	70134	70854	69170	70626	71002	70026	71514	69930	69286	71026	69806	70586	70330	70134	70854	69170	70626	71002	70026	71514	69930	69286	71026	69806	70586	70330												
1163	1158	1020	1052	1172	1024	1181	1175	1050	1041	1053	1165	1033	2008	2003	1865	1897	2017	1869	2026	2020	1895	1886	1898	2010	1878	149	144	6	38	158	10	167	161	36	27	39	151	19	2346	2341	2203	2235	2355	2207	2364	2358	2233	2224	2326	2348	2216	70330
1035	1040	1178	1146	1026	1174	1017	1023	1148	1157	1145	1048	1150	1880	1885	2023	1991	1871	2019	1862	1868	1993	2002	1990	1893	1995	21	26	164	132	12	160	3	9	134	143	131	34	136	2218	2223	2361	2329	2209	2357	2200	2206	2331	2340	2328	2231	2333	70330
1140	1058	1090	1087	1107	1105	1106	1117	1081	1071	1127	1044	1154	1985	1903	1935	1932	1952	1950	1951	1962	1926	1916	1972	1889	1999	126	44	76	73	93	91	92	103	67	57	113	30	140	2323	2241	2273	2270	2290	2288	2289	2300	2264	2254	2310	2227	2337	70330
1031	1167	1110	1100	1095	1102	1088	1082	1116	1135	1063	1057	1141	1876	2012	1955	1945	1940	1947	1933	1927	1961	1980	1908	1902	1986	17	153	96	86	81	88	74	68	102	121	49	43	127	2214	2350	2293	2283	2278	2285	2271	2265	2299	2318	2246	2240	2324	70330
1018	1180	1094	1101	1099	1097	1104	1085	1113	1136	1062	1045	1153	1863	2025	1939	1946	1944	1942	1949	1930	1958	1981	1907	1890	1998	4	166	80	87	85	83	90	71	99	122	48	31	139	2201	2363	2277	2284	2282	2280	2287	2268	2296	2319	2245	2228	2336	70330
1038	1160	1109	1096	1103	1098	1089	1122	1076	1073	1125	1155	1043	1883	2005	1954	1941	1948	1943	1934	1967	1921	1918	1970	2000	1888	24	146	95	82	89	84	75	108	62	59	111	141	29	2221	2343	2292	2279	2286	2281	2272	2305	2259	2256	2308	2338	2226	70330
1171	1027	1092	1111	1091	1093	1108	1121	1077	1068	1130	1151	1047	1876	2012	1937	1956	1936	1938	1953	1966	1922	1913	1975	1996	1892	157	13	78	97	77	79	94	107	63	54	116	137	33	2354	2210	2275	2294	2274	2276	2291	2304	2260	2251	2313	2334	2230	70330
1182	1016	1079	1123	1120	1084	1083	1086	1118	1131	1067	1179	1019	2027	1861	1924	1968	1965	1929	1928	1931	1963	1976	1912	2024	1864	168	2	65	109	106	70	69	72	104	117	53	165	5	2365	2199	2262	2306	2303	2267	2266	2269	2301	2314	2250	2362	2202	70330
1159	1039	1119	1075	1078	1114	1115	1080	1112	1137	1061	1166	1032	2004	1884	1964	1920	1923	1959	1960	1925	1957	1982	1906	2011	1877	145	25	105	61	64	100	101	66	98	123	47	152	18	2342	2222	2302	2258	2261	2297	2298	2263	2295	2320	2244	2349	2215	70330
1168	1030	1138	1064	1069	1133	1072	1070	1139	1074	1132	1042	1156	2013	1875	1983	1909	1914	1978	1917	1915	1984	1919	1977	1887	2001	154	16	124	50	55	119	58	56	125	60	118	28	142	2351	2213	2321	2247	2252	2316	2255	2253	2322	2257	2315	2225	2339	70330
1015	1183	1060	1134	1129	1065	1126	1128	1059	1066	1124	1037	1161	1860	2028	1905	1979	1974	1910	1971	1973	1904	1911	1969	1882	2006	1	169	46	120	115	51	112	114	45	52	110	23	147	2198	2366	2243	2317	2312	2248	2309	2311	2242	2249	2307	2220	2344	70330
1025	1173	1029	1170	1055	1022	1021	1149	1164	1144	1036	1147	1152	1870	2018	1874	2015	1900	1867	1866	1994	2009	1989	1881	1992	1997	11	159	15	156	41	8	7	135	150	130	22	133	138	2208	2356	2212	2353	2238	2205	2204	2332	2347	2327	2219	2330	2325	70330
1142	1056	1169	1028	1143	1102	1177	1049	1034	1054	1162	1051	1046	1987	1901	2014	1873	1988	2021	2022	1894	1879	1899	2007	1896	1891	128	42	155	14	129	162	163	35	20	40	148	37	32	2325	2239	2352	2211	2326	2359	2360	2232	2217	2237	2345	2234	2239	70330
318	313	175	207	327	179	336	330	205	196	208	320	188	2177	2172	2034	2066	2186	2038	2195	2189	2064	2055	2067	2179	2047	1332	1327	1189	1221	1341	1193	1350	1344	1219	1210	1222	1334	1202	1839	1834	1696	1728	1848	1700	1857	1851	1726	1717	1729	1841	1709	70330
190	195	233	301	181	329	172	178	303	312	300	203	305	2049	2054	2192	2160	2040	2188	2031	2037	2162	2171	2159	2062	2164	1204	1209	1347	1315	1195	1343	1186	1192	1317	1326	1314	1217	1319	1711	1716	1854	1822	1702	1850	1693	1699	1824	1833	1821	1724	1826	70330
295	213	345	242	262	260	261	272	236	226	282	199	309	2154	2072	2104	2101	2121	2119	2120	2131	2095	2085	2141	2058	2168	1309	1227	1259	1256	1276	1274	1275	1286	1250	1240	1296	1213	1323	1816	1734	1766	1763	1783	1781	1782	1793	1757	1747	1803	1720	1830	70330
186	322	265	255	250	257	243	237	271	290	218	212	296	2045	2181	2124	2114	2109	2116	2102	2096	2130	2149	2077	2071	2155	1200	1336	1279	1269	1264	1271	1257	1251	1285	1304	1232	1226	1310	1707	1843	1786	1776	1771	1778	1764	1758	1792	1811	1739	1733	1817	70330
173	335	249	256	254	252	259	240	268	291	217	200	308	2032	2194	2108	2115	2113	2111	2118	2099	2127	2150	2076	2059	2167	1187	1349	1263	1270	1268	1266	1273	1254	1282	1305	1231	1214	1322	1694	1856	1770	1777	1775	1773	1760	1761	1789	1812	1738	1721	1829	70330
193	315	264	251	258	253	244	277	231	228	280	310	308	2052	2174	2123	2110	2112	2112	2103	2136	2090	2087	2139	2169	2057	1207	1329	1278	1265	1272	1267	1258	1291	1245	1243	1294	1324	1212	1714	1836	1785	1772	1779	1774	1765	1798	1752	1749	1801	1831	1719	70330
326	182	247	266	246	248	263	276	232	223	285	306	202	2185	2041	2106	2125	2105	2107	2122	2135	2091	2182	2144	2165	2061	1340	1196	1261	1280	1260	1262	1277	1290	1246	1237	1299	1320	1216	1847	1703	1768	1787	1767	1769	1784	1797	1753	1744	1806	1827	1723	70330
337	171	234	278	275	239	238	241	273	286	222	334	174	2196	2030	2093	2137	2134	2098	2097	2100	2132	2145	2081	2193	2033	1351	1185	1248	1292	1289	1253	1252	1255	1287	1300	1236	1348	1188	1858	1692	1755	1799	1796	1760	1759	1762	1794	1807	1743	1855	1695	70330
314	194	274	230	233	269	270	235	267	292	216	321	187	2173	2053	2133	2089	2092	2128	2129	2094	2126	2151	2075	2180	2046	1328	1208	1288	1244	1247	1283	1284	1249	1281	1306	1230	1335	1201	1835	1715	1795	1751	1754	1790	1791	1756	1788	1813	1737	1842	1708	70330
323	185	293	219	224	288	227	225	294	229	287	197	311	2182	2044	2152	2078	2083	2147	2086	2084	2153	2088	2146																													

18	mgc	70790	70002	70414	69090	70854	69722	70942	70670	70330	70518	70350	70278	70330	70790	70002	70414	69090	70854	69722	70942	70670	70330	70518	70350	70278	70330	70790	70002	70414	69090	70854	69722	70942	70670	70330	70518	70350	70278	70330														
1132	1060	1062	1064	1065	1128	1126	1124	1130	1141	1057	1025	1173	1977	1905	1907	1909	1910	1973	1971	1969	1975	1986	1902	1870	2018	118	46	48	50	51	114	112	110	116	127	43	11	159	2315	2243	2245	2247	2248	2311	2309	2307	2313	2324	2240	2208	2356	70330		
1139	1082	1086	1084	1119	1120	1122	1080	1059	1050	1148	1183	1015	1984	1927	1931	1929	1964	1965	1967	1925	1904	1895	1993	2028	1860	125	68	72	70	105	106	108	66	45	36	134	169	1	2322	2265	2269	2267	2302	2303	2305	2263	2242	2233	2331	2366	2198	70330		
1137	1123	1090	1087	1107	1105	1106	1075	1061	1147	1051	1176	1022	1982	1968	1935	1932	1952	1950	1951	1920	1906	1992	1896	2021	1867	123	109	76	73	93	91	92	61	47	133	37	162	8	2320	2306	2273	2270	2290	2288	2289	2258	2244	2330	2234	2359	2205	70330		
1135	1121	1100	1100	1095	1102	1088	1077	1063	1045	1153	1178	1020	1980	1966	1955	1945	1940	1947	1933	1922	1908	1890	1998	2023	1865	121	107	96	86	81	88	74	63	49	31	139	164	6	2318	2304	2293	2283	2278	2285	2271	2260	2246	2228	2336	2361	2203	70330		
1067	1081	1094	1101	1099	1097	1104	1117	1131	1145	1053	1179	1019	1912	1926	1939	1946	1944	1942	1949	1962	1976	1990	1898	2024	1864	53	67	80	87	85	83	90	103	117	131	39	165	5	2250	2264	2277	2284	2282	2280	2287	2300	2314	2328	2236	2362	2202	70330		
1069	1083	1109	1096	1103	1098	1089	1115	1129	1149	1049	1137	1061	1914	1928	1954	1941	1948	1943	1934	1960	1974	1994	1894	1882	2006	55	69	95	82	89	84	75	101	115	35	35	23	147	2252	2266	2292	2279	2286	2281	2272	2298	2312	2332	2232	2220	2344	70330		
1071	1085	1092	1111	1091	1093	1108	1113	1127	1040	1158	1032	1166	1916	1930	1937	1956	1936	1938	1953	1958	1972	1885	2003	1877	2011	57	71	78	97	77	79	94	99	113	26	144	18	152	2254	2268	2275	2294	2274	2276	2291	2296	2310	2223	2341	2215	2349	70330		
1073	1118	1112	1114	1079	1078	1076	1116	1125	1044	1154	1027	1171	1918	1963	1957	1959	1924	1923	1921	1961	1970	1889	1999	1872	2016	59	104	98	100	65	64	62	102	111	30	140	13	157	2256	2301	2295	2297	2262	2261	2259	2299	2308	2227	2337	2210	2354	70330		
1068	1138	1136	1134	1133	1070	1072	1074	1066	1140	1058	1029	1169	1913	1983	1981	1979	1978	1915	1917	1919	1911	1985	1903	1874	2014	54	124	122	120	119	56	58	60	52	126	44	15	155	2251	2321	2319	2317	2316	2253	2255	2257	2249	2323	2241	2212	2352	70330		
1048	1156	1151	1157	1159	1055	1054	1052	1155	1046	1056	1180	1018	1893	2001	1996	2002	2004	1900	1899	1897	2000	1891	1901	2025	1863	34	142	137	143	145	41	40	38	141	32	42	166	4	2231	2339	2334	2340	2342	2238	2237	2235	2338	2229	2239	2363	2201	70330		
1150	1042	1047	1041	1039	1143	1144	1146	1043	1142	1152	1035	1163	1995	1887	1892	1886	1884	1988	1989	1991	1888	1987	1997	1880	2008	136	28	33	27	25	129	130	132	29	128	138	21	149	2333	2225	2230	2224	2222	2326	2327	2329	2226	2325	2335	2218	2346	70330		
1170	1038	1033	1030	1175	1026	1031	1034	1177	1036	1181	1182	1174	2015	1883	1878	1875	2020	1871	1876	1879	2022	1881	2026	2027	2019	156	24	19	16	161	12	17	20	163	22	167	168	160	2353	2221	2216	2213	2358	2209	2214	2217	2360	2219	2364	2365	2357	70330		
1028	1160	1165	1168	1102	1127	1167	1161	1024	1016	1010	1024	1016	1893	2005	2010	2013	1868	2017	2012	2009	1866	2007	1862	2027	2008	1629	1861	14	146	151	154	9	158	153	150	7	148	3	10	2	2211	2343	2348	2351	2206	2355	2350	2347	2204	2345	2200	2207	2199	70330
287	215	217	219	220	283	281	279	285	296	212	180	328	2146	2074	2076	2078	2079	2142	2140	2138	2144	2155	2071	2039	2187	1301	1229	1231	1233	1234	1297	1295	1293	1299	1310	1226	1194	1342	1808	1736	1738	1740	1741	1804	1802	1800	1806	1817	1733	1701	1849	70330		
294	237	241	239	274	275	277	235	214	205	303	338	170	2153	2096	2100	2098	2133	2134	2136	2094	2073	2064	2162	2197	2029	1308	1251	1255	1253	1288	1289	1291	1249	1228	1219	1317	1352	1184	1815	1758	1762	1760	1795	1796	1798	1756	1735	1726	1824	1859	1691	70330		
292	278	245	242	262	260	261	230	216	302	206	331	177	2151	2137	2104	2101	2121	2119	2120	2089	2075	2161	2065	2190	2036	1306	1292	1259	1256	1276	1274	1275	1244	1230	1316	1220	1345	1191	1813	1799	1766	1763	1783	1781	1782	1751	1737	1823	1727	1852	1698	70330		
290	276	265	255	250	257	243	232	218	200	308	333	175	2149	2135	2124	2114	2109	2116	2102	2091	2077	2059	2167	2192	2034	1304	1290	1279	1269	1264	1271	1257	1246	1232	1214	1322	1347	1189	1811	1797	1786	1776	1771	1778	1764	1753	1739	1721	1829	1854	1696	70330		
222	236	249	256	254	252	259	272	286	300	208	334	174	2081	2095	2108	2115	2113	2111	2108	2131	2145	2159	2067	2193	2033	1236	1250	1263	1270	1268	1266	1273	1286	1300	1314	1322	1348	1188	1743	1757	1770	1777	1775	1773	1780	1793	1807	1821	1729	1855	1695	70330		
224	238	264	261	251	258	253	244	270	284	304	204	192	2083	2097	2123	2110	2117	2112	2103	2129	2143	2163	2063	2051	2175	1238	1252	1278	1265	1272	1267	1258	1284	1298	1318	1218	1206	1330	1745	1759	1785	1772	1779	1774	1765	1791	1805	1825	1725	1713	1837	70330		
226	240	247	266	246	248	263	268	282	195	317	321	2085	2099	2106	2125	2105	2107	2122	2127	2141	2054	2172	2046	2180	1240	1254	1261	1280	1260	1262	1277	1282	1296	1209	1327	1201	1335	1747	1761	1768	1787	1767	1769	1784	1789	1803	1716	1834	1708	1842	70330			
228	273	267	269	234	233	231	271	280	199	309	182	326	2087	2132	2126	2128	2093	2092	2100	2130	2139	2058	2168	2041	2185	1242	1287	1281	1283	1248	1247	1245	1285	1294	1213	1323	1196	1340	1749	1794	1788	1790	1755	1754	1752	1792	1801	1720	1830	1707	1847	70330		
223	293	291	289	288	225	227	229	221	295	213	184	324	2082	2152	2150	2148	2147	2084	2086	2088	2080	2154	2072	2043	2183	1237	1307	1305	1303	1302	1239	1241	1243	1235	1309	1227	1198	1338	1744	1814	1812	1810	1809	1746	1748	1750	1742	1816	1734	1705	1845	70330		
203	311	306	312	314	210	209	307	310	201	211	335	173	2062	2170	2165	2171	2173	2069	2068	20																																		

2.3 Magic Squares of Order 39

Below are three examples of magic squares of order 39 obtained from magic squares of order 117. It is obtained by the application of the formula $\frac{a^2 - b^2}{2}$, $a > b$, i.e., subtract $\frac{117^2 - 39^2}{2} := 6084$ from each entry of magic square order 117, we get the following three magic squares of order 52:

3	mgc	28926	28641	28338	27837	27192	26685	26076	25581	24936	24423	24120	23847	23088	23856	25092	26310	27330	28206	29220	30132	31158	32034	33042	34260	35508	36270	35517	35232	34929	34428	33783	33276	32667	32172	31527	31014	30711	30438	29679
521	530	528	526	524	522	520	668	670	672	674	676	665	1366	1375	1373	1371	1369	1367	1365	1513	1515	1517	1519	1521	1510	183	192	190	188	186	184	182	330	332	334	336	338	327	29679	
675	641	633	635	637	639	540	539	537	535	533	643	509	1520	1486	1478	1480	1482	1484	1385	1384	1382	1380	1378	1488	1354	337	303	295	297	299	301	202	201	199	197	195	305	171	29679	
673	532	625	553	555	557	558	621	619	617	623	652	511	1518	1377	1470	1398	1400	1402	1403	1466	1464	1462	1468	1497	1356	335	194	287	215	217	219	220	283	281	279	285	314	173	29679	
671	534	632	575	579	577	612	613	615	573	552	650	513	1516	1379	1477	1420	1424	1422	1457	1458	1460	1418	1397	1495	1358	333	196	294	237	241	239	274	275	277	235	214	312	175	29679	
669	536	630	616	583	580	600	598	599	568	554	648	515	1514	1381	1475	1461	1428	1425	1445	1443	1444	1413	1399	1493	1360	331	198	292	278	245	242	262	260	261	230	216	310	177	29679	
667	538	628	614	603	593	588	595	581	570	556	646	517	1512	1383	1473	1459	1448	1438	1433	1440	1426	1415	1401	1491	1362	329	200	290	276	265	255	250	257	243	232	218	308	179	29679	
666	642	560	574	602	594	592	590	582	610	624	542	518	1511	1487	1405	1419	1447	1439	1437	1435	1427	1455	1469	1387	1363	328	304	222	236	264	256	254	252	244	272	286	204	180	29679	
523	640	562	576	587	589	596	591	597	608	622	544	661	1368	1485	1407	1421	1432	1434	1441	1436	1442	1453	1467	1389	1506	185	302	224	238	249	251	258	253	259	270	284	206	323	29679	
525	638	564	578	585	604	584	586	601	606	620	546	659	1370	1483	1409	1423	1430	1449	1429	1431	1446	1451	1465	1391	1504	187	300	226	240	247	266	246	248	263	268	282	208	321	29679	
527	636	566	611	605	607	572	571	569	609	618	548	657	1372	1481	1411	1456	1450	1452	1417	1416	1414	1454	1463	1393	1502	189	298	228	273	267	269	234	233	231	271	280	210	319	29679	
529	634	561	631	629	627	626	563	565	567	559	550	655	1374	1479	1406	1476	1474	1472	1471	1408	1410	1412	1404	1395	1500	191	296	223	293	291	289	288	225	227	229	221	212	317	29679	
531	541	551	549	547	545	644	645	647	649	651	543	653	1376	1386	1396	1394	1392	1390	1489	1490	1492	1494	1496	1388	1498	193	203	213	211	209	207	306	307	309	311	313	205	315	29679	
519	654	656	658	660	662	664	516	514	512	510	508	663	1364	1499	1501	1503	1505	1507	1509	1361	1359	1357	1355	1353	1508	181	316	318	320	322	324	326	178	176	174	172	170	325	29679	
352	361	359	357	355	353	351	499	501	503	505	507	496	690	699	697	695	693	691	689	837	839	841	843	845	834	1028	1037	1035	1033	1031	1029	1027	1175	1177	1179	1181	1183	1172	29679	
506	472	464	466	468	470	371	370	368	366	364	474	340	844	810	802	804	806	808	709	708	706	704	702	812	678	1182	1148	1140	1142	1144	1146	1047	1046	1044	1042	1040	1150	1016	29679	
504	363	456	384	386	388	389	452	450	448	454	483	342	842	701	794	722	724	726	727	790	788	786	792	821	680	1180	1039	1132	1060	1062	1064	1065	1128	1126	1124	1130	1159	1018	29679	
502	365	463	406	410	408	443	444	446	404	383	481	344	840	703	801	744	748	746	781	782	784	742	721	819	682	1178	1041	1139	1082	1086	1084	1119	1120	1122	1080	1059	1157	1020	29679	
500	367	461	447	414	411	431	429	430	399	385	479	346	838	705	799	785	752	749	769	767	768	737	723	817	684	1176	1043	1137	1123	1090	1087	1107	1105	1106	1075	1061	1155	1022	29679	
498	369	459	445	434	424	419	426	412	401	387	477	348	836	707	797	783	772	762	757	764	750	739	725	815	686	1174	1045	1135	1121	1110	1100	1095	1102	1088	1077	1063	1153	1024	29679	
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1271	1266	1267	1262	1274	1255	1281	1302	1234	1310	1226	1194	1342	88	83	84	79	91	72	98	119	51	127	43	11	159	933	928	929	924	936	917	943	964	896	972	888	856	1004	29679	
1264	1268	1272	1261	1275	1248	1288	1293	1243	1219	1317	1352	1184	81	85	89	78	92	65	105	110	60	36	134	169	1	926	930	934	923	937	910	950	955	905	881	979	1014	846	29679	
1269	1270	1265	1279	1257	1251	1285	1297	1239	1316	1220	1345	1191	86	87	82	96	74	68	102	114	56	133	37	162	8	931	932	927	941	919	913	947	959	901	978	882	1007	853	29679	
1273	1277	1276	1258	1256	1254	1282	1295	1241	1209	1327	1347	1189	90	94	93	75	73	71	99	112	58	26	144	164	6	935	939	938	920	918	916	944	957	903	871	989	1009	851	29679	
1263	1259	1260	1280	1278	1290	1246	1232	1304	1314	1222	1348	1188	80	76	77	97	95	107	63	49	121	131	39	165	5	925	921	922	942	940	952	908	894	966	976	884	1010	850	29679	
1253	1289	1252	1249	1291	1292	1250	1235	1301	1318	1218	1206	1330	70	106	69	66	108	109	67	52	118	135	35	23	147	915	951	914	911	953	954	912	897	963	980	880	868	992	29679	
1283	1247	1284	1287	1245	1286	1244	1296	1240	1214	1322	1201	1335	100	64	101	104	62	103	61	113	57	31	139	18	152	945	909	946	949	907	948	906	958	902	876	984	863	997	29679	
1231	1230	1294	1300	1299	1298	1228	1229	1303	1213	1323	1196	1340	48	47	111	117	116	115	45	46	120	30	140	13	157	893	892	956	962	961	960	890	891	965	875	985	858	1002	29679	
1305	1306	1242	1236	1237	1238	1308	1233	1307	1309	1227	1198	1338	122	123	59	53	54	55	125	50	124	126	44	15																

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